

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
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**DIAGNOSTIC AND PROGNOSTIC AMPLIFIERS OF
ELECTROCARDIOGRAMS IN INTELLIGENT MEDICAL EQUIPMENT
AYNUR Jabiyeva J. ¹, GULNARA Isgandarova Sh².**

^{1, 2}Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Department of Instrumentation Engineering, Azerbaijan,
Baku, str.20, AZE 1010

¹ Dosent, <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0336-8586>, Aynur.Jabiyeva@outlook.com, 050-344-99-54, AZE 1010

² Assistent. <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6321-2524>, gulnareshahin21@gmail.com, 055-445-00-08, AZE 1009

Abstract

Modern medicine widely uses physical methods of diagnosis, prevention and treatment of diseases that require the use of special equipment. In addition, many different technical devices, instruments and apparatus are used for auxiliary purposes in medicine. We call the collection of all technical tools used in medicine "medical technology". Essentially the most important is the field of medical technology that uses the phenomenon of electric current, involving a large number of sophisticated instruments and apparatus. Electromedical equipment is usually based on physiotherapeutic equipment used in the field of light and electrotherapy, methods of electrical stimulation of tissues (electrodiagnosis) and biopotentials (electrocardiography, etc.). The development of electromedical equipment took place together with the general development of electrical engineering, and then radio engineering. Electromedical equipment, electrostatic machines, galvanic cells, and somewhat later induction coils began to develop when artificial sources of electricity became available for experimentation. These electrical sources were used in the first methods of electrical therapy, such as franklinization (static shower), galvanization, and later ionogalvanization and faradization, along with electrodiagnosis using the classical method. Artificial light sources in phototherapy were mainly arc lamps and later powerful incandescent lamps (Sollux lamps). The development of radiotechnics has led to the creation of a new field of physical methods for the treatment of electrotherapy with high-frequency currents.

Keywords

Elektrokardioqram, gücləndiricilər intellektual tibbi avadanlıqlar, biopotensiallar, kardioqraf;

Electrocardiogram, amplifiers, Intelligent medical equipment, biopotentials, cardiograph;

Электрокардиограмма, усилители, интеллектуальное медицинское оборудование,

биопотенциалы, кардиограф.

1.INTRODUCTION

The electrocardiogram (ECG) signal is widely used in diagnosing heart diseases. Since the amplitude of this signal is very small, a low noise amplifier with high gain and high common mode rejection is required. In portable devices, the battery provides the necessary power to the electrocardiogram (ECG) device. Therefore, the area and power consumption of ECG amplifiers should be small. As is known, when processing signals in electronic devices, in most cases it is necessary to pre-amplify them; for this purpose, amplifiers of various types are used [1]. This paper proposes an

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instrumentation amplifier for ECG applications, where it is used to reduce the area of a circuit that is inherently nonlinear, and presents a method to reduce the impact of this nonlinearity. A common analog processor is an operational amplifier. More recently, applications in biology have benefited from wireless fabrication with extremely low power consumption, low voltage, low coupling, and high precision. The present study examines the relationship between the validity of medical or low-frequency energy experiments shown in a number of literature publications. The wireless comparison takes into account linearity, technological advances, supply voltage, power consumption, frequency, and how they are used in biomedical signal processing. Future researchers will benefit from this text as they work to improve wireless connectivity for low frequency, linear, and biological applications.

Amplifiers are used in both receiving and transmitting equipment, as well as auxiliary signal conversion devices. In addition to the basic parameters (rated output power, sensitivity, efficiency, etc.), an important characteristic of amplifiers is the degree of reliability and acceptable operating conditions. These modes determine the maximum permissible climatic, mechanical, biological and many other factors under which the equipment must maintain its functionality [2]. In other words, they must be capable of operating under stringent conditions with a high level of reliability, while at the same time providing minimal distortion across the entire range of amplified frequencies, that is, they must accurately represent the input waveform at the output. To amplify signals carrying audio information, low-frequency amplifiers are most often used; in these cases they are called sound amplifiers. In addition, in various fields: measurement technology and flaw detection; automation, telemechanics and analog computer technology; in other branches of the electronics industry, etc., it is used to enhance the information signal. An audio amplifier usually consists of an amplifier and a power amplifier (PA). The preamplifier is designed to increase power and voltage and bring them to the values necessary for the operation of the final power amplifier; often includes a volume control, tone control, or equalizer; sometimes it can be built as a separate device. The power amplifier must provide the specified electrical oscillation power to the load (consumer) circuit.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND PURPOSE OF WORK

The cause of nonlinear distortions, as a rule, is the nonlinearity of the current-voltage characteristics of the amplifier elements (transistors, lamps), as well as incorrectly selected modes of their operation. As a result of nonlinear distortions, when a purely sinusoidal signal is amplified, additional harmonic components appear in the output signal, i.e. the harmonic composition of the input signal changes [3]. Experience shows that devices based on cascaded operational amplifiers have the best electrical characteristics. The relevance of such schemes is dictated by their high profitability and efficiency, simplicity of design, management and operation, as well as compactness and relatively low cost. Therefore, this article is devoted to presenting a prototype of such an amplifier, the operation of which is based on the dependence of a three-electrode lamp on the network potential: the positive potential in the network increases, and the negative potential - the anode current of the lamp decreases.

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Figure 1. Schematic diagram (a) and operation diagram (b) of a simple amplifier

Schematic diagram of a simple amplifier with a three-electrode lamp Figure 1, a. In the figure, graph 1, b explains its operation. In the anode circuit of the lamp, resistance R_a is connected in series with the power source. The amplified voltage u_c is supplied to the lamp network. A change in voltage in the network causes fluctuations in the anode current $\dot{I}$ (Fig. 1, b). Current $\dot{I}_a$ is created in resistance R_a due to a voltage drop that has a pulsating nature. The alternating component of this voltage is extracted through the coupling capacitor $U_a C_p$ and represents the amplified voltage: $U_a = k u_c$, where k is called the gain. In amplifiers used in biopotential recording devices, the shape of the output voltage must exactly match the shape of the voltage supplied to the network, that is, the amplifier must operate without distortion. Distortions are divided into nonlinear ones in frequency; they arise when operating outside the linear part of the network characteristics, and are also associated with the appearance of the current voltage in the network in positive half-cycles, accompanied by a decrease in internal voltage. The network potential leads to resistance of the potential source in the network, as a result of which the network potential itself decreases. To avoid nonlinear distortions with precise characteristics, the operating mode of the amplifier is limited to the linear part.

In addition, by increasing the anode voltage and applying additional constant negative voltage to the network (Fig. 2, a), the network characteristic changes along with the operating point, so that the potential in the network generally remains negative. times, and therefore the amplifier operates without mains current (Fig. 2, b). The auxiliary voltage is supplied to the network either from a separate source (Fig. 2, a), or the voltage drop from the constant component of the anode current across the resistance is used,

Figure. 2. Schematic diagram of the amplifier (a) and operation diagram (b)

It is included in the cathode circuit with a bias in the network. Resistance R_K is passed through capacitor C_K of a sufficiently large capacity, through which the alternating component of the anode current passes.

In DC incandescent amplifiers, the bias voltage can be obtained using a resistor in series with the incandescent circuit in a wire connected to the amplifier's negative common terminal.

C_K is removed not from the resistance connected to the anode circuit of the lamp, but from the resistance R_K , connected in parallel with the lamp itself through the expansion capacitor R_a . This does not change the principle of formation of increased voltage.

Between the grid and the cathode of the lamp, a resistance R_c is usually included, which is necessary to ensure leakage of electrons falling on the grid, especially if there is a coupling capacitor C_c in the grid circuit; the leakage resistance, together with the capacitance of the coupling capacitor, determines the time constant of the grid circuit, which is important for the operating characteristics of the amplifier.

Inductance (for example, the windings of galvanometer electromagnets) is due to the fact that the value of their resistance depends on frequency. Therefore, the gain will be different for simple (harmonic) oscillations, into which a given oscillation of a complex shape can be decomposed. This will lead to a distortion of the voltage waveform at the output of the amplifier compared to the mains voltage. This and distortion are taken into account using the frequency response of the amplifier, which gives the dependence of the gain on the frequency k of harmonic oscillations ν (Fig. 3). It has a characteristic almost horizontal midsection and provides attenuation in both the x- and high-frequency regions. The limits of the oscillation frequency corresponding to the horizontal part of the characteristic and therefore amplifying without distortion are called the gain band. The amplifier's bandwidth must correspond to the boundaries of the amplified harmonic spectrum (i.e., the frequency range of harmonic oscillations into which a complex oscillation can be decomposed).

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Figure 3. Amplifier frequency response

For the electrocardiogram, the main ones are low frequencies in the range of 1-10 Hz, but the full harmonic spectrum of the electrocardiogram has frequencies from about 0.5. 100 g. Therefore, the frequency response of the electrocardiograph should have a horizontal part, starting from the lowest frequencies of the order of fractions of a hertz. In this case, it is desirable to sharply reduce the characteristics in the high-frequency region (above 100 GHz) so that the amplifier does not pass higher-frequency currents, external interference, muscle biocurrents falling on the electrodes, etc.

if the gain of the lamp is insufficient, the amplified voltage in the first lamp, through a decoupling capacitor, enters the network of the second lamp, etc. The result is a multi-stage or multi-stage amplifier.

To record biopotentials, amplifiers with rheostatic-capacitive coupling between cascades are used, which ensures the least distortion. Such an amplifier cannot amplify DC voltage due to the presence of coupling capacitors. When a constant voltage is applied to the input of the amplifier, the capacitors are charged and an increasing voltage appears at the amplifier output, but then the capacitors are gradually discharged through shunt resistors and the voltage at the amplifier output decreases. The rate of this decrease depends on the magnitude of the resistances and capacitances in the network circuits of the amplifier and is characterized by a "time constant", that is, at a constant input voltage of the amplifier, the output voltage decreases by $\frac{1}{e} = \frac{1}{2,72} = 0,37$, which is its original size. The amplifier's time constant characterizes the degree of distortion of low-frequency oscillations (below 1 Hz), which by their nature

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are more similar to direct current. The longer the time constant, the less distorted these oscillations are. In electrocardiographs, the time constant is 1.5-1.8 seconds.

The amplifier also uses a push-pull circuit. The alternating voltage to be amplified is switched between the networks of both lamps. Therefore, due to the middle between the cathodes, the potentials of the networks and, consequently, the oscillations of the anode current in the lamps are in antiphase: as the anode current increases in one lamp, it decreases in the other, and vice versa. In this case, since the power supply is connected to the midpoint of the resistance, R_a represents the alternating component of the voltage drop caused by the anode. The lamp currents in both halves of this resistance are directed towards each other, and they are additionally in antiphase, that is, since they are opposite in sign, they come together as a single whole in the resistance R_a . Therefore, the total voltage that can be extracted from this resistance through the isolation capacitors is exactly the same as the voltage connected between the networks of lamps n, but has a much larger amplitude.

Typically, a bias voltage is applied to the grid and lamps, which changes the anode-grid characteristics of the lamps.

If an alternating voltage is applied to the amplifier, it generates The grids of both lamps have the same potential relative to the common point of the cathodes; this will cause the anode currents of both lamps to oscillate in phase (i.e., out of phase). In this case, the alternating components of the voltage drop on both halves of the resistance, directed in the opposite direction, formed by the anode currents of the lamps, neutralize each other. In practice, due to the incomplete symmetry of both halves of the circuit, their complete destruction does not occur, but common-mode signals in a push-pull amplifier are amplified to a lesser extent than operational signals supplied to tube networks in antiphase.

Figure 4. Differential amplifier

In this regard, the networks of both lamps are called push-pull differential amplifiers and are widely used in devices for recording biopotentials, since they can significantly reduce the influence of

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induced potentials, which are in most cases in phase. This differential amplifier characteristic can be further improved by using strong negative feedback.

It is carried out by supplying part of the voltage from the output of the amplifier to its input, that is, in the anode circuit to the network circuit. Feedback can be positive if the mains voltage is applied in phase with the input signal and the gain increases. Positive feedback is mainly used in generators. If the mains voltage is applied out of phase with the input, the feedback in the signal may be negative and hence the gain is reduced. Negative feedback is often used in low frequency amplifiers where the amplifier reduces distortion and improves stability.

This is carried out by turning on resistance R_k to (Fig. 4), which in this case is not maneuvered by the capacitor and the anode current completely passes through it.

A differential amplifier with negative feedback can greatly reduce the gain of common mode signals (i.e. interference). At the same time, for antiphase oscillations (i.e., for the operating signal), negative feedback about the resistance R_k is practically not created: these oscillations, passing through the resistance R_k and in antiphase, are removed and completely cancel each other out. symmetry of the circuit.

Some devices (not just electrocardiographs) have a lamp stage (Fig. 5) called a special cathode follower.

The latter is a triode in the network from which the control signals are given, and the resistance R_x is connected to the cathode circuit, which is a load or resistance from which the output voltage is removed.

Figure 5. The voltage across the resistor

The voltage on the resistor R_x repeats the shape of the signals supplied to the lamp network, as in the conventional amplification circuit, but the gain in this case is less than unity due to the strong negative

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feedback implemented using this resistance. Typically, the purpose of the cathode follower after turn-on is to match the output impedance of the amplifier stage to the low-impedance load resistance.

3.RESULTS

In practical amplifier circuits, lamps (pentodes) are often used, in addition to the control network, two more are connected: a fuse, which significantly improves the performance and characteristics of the protective lamp.

Figure 6. Lamps (pentodes) in practical amplifier circuits

In the article, a protective network equipped with a constant positive voltage close to the anode voltage (after the control network) reduces the effect of the voltage change on the anode of the lamp on the anode current, which is caused by the voltage change on the anode resistance R_a . In addition, the protective network reduces the capacitance between the anode and the control network, which has a detrimental effect on the operation of high-frequency amplifiers and oscillators. The protective network is usually connected to the positive pole of the power source through an additional resistance R_e and connected to the cathode through a capacitor C_e .

Figure 6. The protective grid

The protective grid (between the protective grid and the anode) is designed to prevent the formation of a secondary emission current between the anode and the protective grid, (Fig 6) the potential of the latter being higher than the potential of the anode. The protective grid is connected to the cathode and, due to its negative potential, pushes secondary electrons back to the anode.

4. CONCLUSIONS

ECG systems use a controlled right leg circuit to amplify the amplifier. In this paper, class AB buffer is used to implement this scheme. Simulation results show that the proposed amplifier has a gain of 46.18 dB and its input noise is 7.8 μ V rms over the frequency range of 0.3 Hz to 150 Hz. The total power consumption of the designed amplifier is 72 nW. The amplifier has a CMRR of 96 dB and a total harmonic distortion (THD) of 0.68% (at 60 Hz). There is a special type of tube called a beam tetrode, which is similar to pentodes. . Due to the special design of the electrodes and the proximity of the anodes, directional screens connected to the cathode inside the lamp create conditions that prevent the formation of secondary current in these lamps.

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